

AN AFROCENTRIC CRITIQUE OF SOUTH AFRICA'S CONTEMPORARY KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION REGIME

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Abstract

The politics of knowledge in the world are as old as the cradle of human civilisation. The stakes of knowledge politics are higher in countries that have a rich history of colonialism, such as South Africa, Namibia and Zimbabwe, among others. In the post-apartheid South Africa, there has been a raging scholarly and policy debate about the dynamics of the knowledge industry within our shores. At the centre of this debate has been the role of statutory institutions, such as ASSAf, NRF, universities and research councils. Despite the expressed legislative framework, the role of these institutions in terms of knowledge generation and development has not been applied in line with this framework by their administrators. The policy makers have not yet seriously held them accountable. The consequence is that these administrators have been largely acting not within the national policy framework. In fact, this discourse has largely assumed the form of a conversation between the deaf. Drawing from the fusion of an alternative Afrocentric perspective and interdisciplinary discourse analysis in its broadest form, this paper argues that statutory institutions have an important national role to play in the knowledge industry. But their activities are not above board. If left operating the way they do, their wrong activities have a potential to undermine declared policy measures to the pursuit of true and quality knowledge.

Keywords: Afrocentricity, Institutions, Knowledge, South Africa, Statute.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5571.2023.002542

1. Introduction

Since time immemorial inter-group relations have defined the nature of life in the world. Such relations have positively or negatively impacted the evolution of life in different sectors and at varying levels. To this end, South Africa's knowledge industry is no exception [1]. While South Africa's knowledge industry is made up of several stakeholders, the primary focus of this paper is on the National Research Foundation (NRF), Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf) and universities-research councils interface. The establishment of the NRF, ASSAf, institutions of higher learning (i. e. University of Limpopo, University of Pretoria and University of Mpumalanga) and research councils (i.e. Human Sciences Research Council and Council for Scientific and Industrial Research) finds expression in South Africa's legislative framework [2–4]. NRF, ASSAf and universities-research councils are legislatively required to lead public efforts to generate and disseminate quality knowledge based on cutting edge research. The good intentions and work, done by these institutions, cannot be taken away. But the manifestations of inter group relations in terms of their work also show that the very institutions that are established to make a meaningful contribution towards knowledge economy are also trapped into the politics that corrode their founding missions and visions. In support of this view for example, Higgins laments that "... NRF policy with regard to research funding in the humanities has as its perhaps unintentional effects the declining rather than the supporting of the humanities" [1].

Consequent to the above, this paper seeks to explore the dynamics and implications of selected statutory institutions on knowledge generation and development in South Africa. The good work of these institutions is well accounted for in their annual reports [5]. These reports cannot be simply taken as a received idea. They need to be interrogated using a multivariate of tools. Hence, there are serious issues about their work that negatively affect the knowledge industry in South Africa [6, 7]. Such issues do not often find their way in institutions' annual reports or let alone, scholarly and popular reports. The central question, grappled with in this paper, is: To what extent are the dynamics of statutory institutions regressing against knowledge development? To answer this question, the author heavily relies on the fusion of Afrocentric theory and interdisciplinary discourse analysis in its broadest form.

Therefore, the aim of the research for this paper was to critique the contemporary knowledge production regime of South Africa through the Afrocentric lens.

2. Methodological and theoretical axis

This paper is based on the theory of Afrocentricity as articulated by Asante [8]. The choice of this theory was largely driven by the desire to use this paper to also contribute towards epistemic justice. This is because Afrocentricity possesses both the cognitive and functional abilities [9]. At the heart of Afrocentricity is the strong belief and convictions that research about African issues should be centred on the history, culture and the lived experiences of the Africans [8]. It is only when the generated data is grounded and orientated on the cultural value systems of the Africans (including African thought system) that a genuinely African perspective can be produced. Such a perspective is important as it is the only valid truth for the Africans, crucial for their socio-political and economic liberation. Any knowledge about Africa, which is based on foreign tools and standards, runs a risk of being riddled with gross substantive errors [10]. This argument does not in any way suggest that theories, rooted outside the continent, have no value in the study of Africa. The key issue is that there is absolutely nothing good to be derived from Western theories that Afrocentricity cannot offer [8]. However, there are strong traditions that straddle Western and non-Western scholarship. For example, critical theory and post-modernism do not presume objectivity.

As a qualitative study, this paper has relied heavily on interdisciplinary discourse analysis. The discourse analysed is either written and/or spoken by South Africans, in the new democratic dispensation. The discussion randomly ranges over racial, age-based, status- or managerial position based “groups, insider/outsider, expert/ non-expert and radical/ non-radical distinctions. The emerging discourse is herein presented in themes and sub-themes, and then synthesised with an Afrocentric lens. The Afrocentric lens embraces the prominent influence of the author/researcher as the leading figure in the operationalisation of research and reporting of the findings [11]. To this end, the epistemic location of this paper forces it to elide the presumed objectivity that is often claimed by Western scholarship without any sound basis. While the paper rejects the binaries in knowledge production, it is worth highlighting, that the author is not concerned about the quantification of data but explanation and description of the phenomena under study [12]. In terms of positionality, the author of this paper is a Black South African. He sought to use his impeccable lived experience as a knowledge worker to expose the biases in the internal workings of key South African knowledge institutions. In terms of epistemic identity, the author is of the Afrocentric tradition. This is not a borrowed epistemic identity and but it inborn to the author. Regardless of the nature of the findings that it glosses hereunder, it cannot be withdrawn willy-nilly and by anybody who has never announced it [13].

3. Result and discussion

3. 1. NRF in Perspective

In terms of the National Research Foundation Act (Act No 23 of 1998), NRF is an independent funding agency, mandated by the government to promote South Africa’s research agenda through the enhancement of knowledge production across all academic disciplines, capacitating high-end human capital and availing funding infrastructure for the research community [4]. Among the mechanisms, used by the NRF to achieve its goals, is the evaluation and rating of researchers. This system is prestigious in form and content. In fact, it is generally the desire of each and every serious academic to obtain NRF rating. Rating of a researcher also attracts prestige for his/her institution. As such, universities invest time, energy and resources to prepare their researchers for rating. The researchers that are already rated are also sought after by many universities in terms of recruitment and retention. The desire by researchers to obtain and retain their rating leads to their continued production of quality scientific knowledge. Normally, NRF evaluation and rating is based on the scholarly contributions of an academic over a period of 8 years. Particular attention is paid to 5 best research outputs during the period under review and based on a set criterion, discipline specific review panels (with the assistance of national and international reviewers) make a judgement.

But it is not all rosy with the NRF rating system. Some of the review panels are dominated by white conservatives and with a few co-opted African foreign nationals [14]. The compromised composition of review panels often produces questionable feedback in relation to some scholars. In most of these panels the agenda is set by whites and Indians and, their coloured followers. In such arranged panels, it should be difficult for African foreign national to go against the voice of the non-Black South African majority. It may be easy to dismiss this reality as constituting an insult to the agency and expertise Black expatriate academics in South Africa more especially because the mechanisations unmasked normally happen behind closed corridors. And those who should be exposing it prefer silence and maintenance of the status quo as long as the current political economy of the knowledge industry is self-serving to them. The publication space in some journals is even staged managed in a way that ensures that this vital debate does not find the necessary academic, policy and public attention. I should hasten to point out that this observation is not aimed at setting one nationality or race against the other. But it is real that some panels are not reflective of the population dynamics of South Africa. A case in point is the Political Science and Philosophy panel. In this panel, there is not a single Black South African. This should be an embarrassment to the NRF, especially given the fact that Political Science and Philosophy disciplines remain deeply un-transformed. The foregoing observation is debatable because the convenor of this panel is an Indian. But still, some Indians are known to only regard themselves as Black when it is convenient for themselves. It is the well-considered view of this paper, that some Black academics are aware about the existence of racist tendencies within the NRF circles. But they choose not to voice it out, so that they do not lose their non-Black friends. Equally important, they choose to mute about the subtle racism in NRF circles because whites are known for being quick to shoot down any argument that uses race as a base to be politically motivated [15]).

It is important to categorially state, that the fact that these institutions, such as NRF and others under study, do not respect national policies is such that they are active participants in the continued marginalisation of Africans who constitute the decisive majority of the South African population, particularly in the knowledge production. One of their consequences is that minorities continue being influential in South Africa. However, majoritarian Black South Africans are partly responsible for this dilemma. Academics and intellectuals of Black South African origin need a serious programme of action to reclaim the ideational space in their country.

Contextually, the panel (Political Science and Philosophy) referred to above has previously rated a white academic at one white university as a C2 researcher. It turned out that such an applicant was even surprised as s/he published one article in two years. Clearly, a recurrent year interruption in terms of publishing was simply overlooked in the evaluation of this application. This can best be explained by the fact that the panel is predominantly white and like it, the applicant belongs to the mainstream. It can well be argued by the NRF that in rating what matters most is the quality rather than the quantity of the research outputs produced. Hence, it is not uncommon for some of those who publish extensively to be non-rated or lowly rated. The latter is often justified through an argument that they churn so many articles in weak journals, that is those with low impact factor. The position of the NRF is in extreme antagonism with the pressures, faced by universities, in terms of the corporatisation of the research enterprise. Thus, the Department of Higher Education and Training's (DHET) subsidy system for publication earning is based on the number of research outputs in peer reviewed publications. What can be deduced from the foregoing is that the NRF's expectations for the researchers are not necessarily in line with the DHET's operational framework and practice [16].

The truth of the matter is that those who are engaged in protest/ radical scholarship are never rated fairly. Some still apply for rating knowing well that the rating system is colonised. But they simply submit to it, so that they can access the rating incentive. This implies that some scholars do not do rating because they want to get to the bottom of truth in terms of their research performance.

Meanwhile, the rating system of the NRF also seems not to be only guided by the stated criteria in terms of research performance. Most of the panels of the NRF seem to be obsessed with gerontocracy or ageing [17]. It would appear, that issues of age and to a certain extent, managerial status and gender also form an un-official or un-declared criterion for evaluations and rating. The

combination of the foregoing largely makes the outcome of the rating applications predictable. In this regard, the problem does not start with the NRF per se. In fact, the Designated Authorities (DAs) are also complicit to some of the questionable outcomes of the rating applications. Experience shows that NRF often endorses the recommendation of the universities' DAs. For example, it is common knowledge, that regardless of a researcher's scholarly standing s/he will be awarded a Y rating as long as s/he is below the age of forty. An exceptional case is the few young white academics who are lucky to be considered for a P rating. Also, those above the age of forty years are normally considered for C rating when they submit their applications for the first time. Regardless of one's scholarly prowess, they are never accorded a B rating on the first application. In some white universities, young but competent scholars' applications are at times rejected by the DAs without any sound basis. The NRF does not robustly engage with the recommendations of DAs in terms of evaluations and rating. A case in point was the C2 rating that was granted to a very weak Executive Officer at one university. Such an applicant hardly had five sole authored articles. But s/he was highly rated better than scholars who have published extensively. How this happened is difficult to fathom except that it makes a mockery out of the NRF rating system.

The feedback from the NRF is also not helpful, especially to those who are engaged in epistemic defiance – an emerging wave towards epistemic justice whose tide is strong in the humanities. For example, the work that is not fixated in mainstream disciplinary boundaries is wrongly described as incoherent. This attitude of some of the NRF review panels reflects their ignorance of interdisciplinary research niche area, such as Africanity and/or Strategic Studies. In looking at the best 5 research outputs in the past 8 years, a case of featuring a publication in one South African journal is lamented. That a top South African journal in Public Affairs is regarded by the panel of Political Science and Philosophy as not reputable raises more questions than answers. It may not be far-fetched that such a baseless criticism cannot be delinked from the fact that two out of the three panel members have a link with the University of Pretoria, an institution that has an ugly past with the owner and publisher of the journal in question [18]. To prove the inconsistency of the review panels, some panels in the Natural Sciences do not see anything wrong in highly rating a scholar who has a majority of his/her publications in one national journal and worse, most of such publications being co-authored. Perhaps, this could be explained by what Peter Vale [19] terms "... governmental emphasis on science and technology; the political emphasis on the economically-grounded idea of "developmentalism". What follows here is that logically, the NRF demands, imposed on the evaluation and rating of research in the natural sciences, may be lower than those in the humanities. This should be understood within the context that in the un-written script of the NRF, the humanities are not scientific enough and consequently, economically un-viable. While the author has a 1st hand account of the problems in the Public Affairs cluster, it would appear that the most of the aspects of the entire knowledge production regime of South Africa are flawed.

3. 2. ASSAf: Reconsidered?

Just like in the business of the NRF, the work of ASSAf is largely defined by the minority. Among the immediate tasks of ASSAf in terms of the promotion of quality scholarship includes a regular review of journals [2]. Unlike books that are naturally demanding in terms of the duration for completion, journals timely report on the findings about topical and relevant issues within their scope. Unfortunately, ASSAf operations are at times hijacked to achieve a narrow political cause, which does not have any material benefit for the pursuit of truth [16]. These sad developments happen especially when journal reviewers sacrifice national interests in favour of personal or sectional interests.

For example, a closer scrutiny of some of ASSAf's reports show that they are riddled with deliberate distortion of facts, which cannot be left unchallenged [20]. In some of these reports, the editorial leadership of some journals are juniorised without any sound basis. Full Professors labelled as promising scholars. This problem is not limited to ASSAf circles. It can be observed within the NRF and some universities in South Africa. In the NRF, a Professor, attached to a university, will be characterised as a promising scholar. It is also not uncommon in some universities for Professors to be awarded as emerging researchers or at worst, characterised as merely "gentle-

man” or “adult male colleague” without any consequences [21]. The big question that can be asked in this regard is that if a scholar is considered as emerging by the NRF or ASSAf, then what is s/he professing? Perhaps this is reflective of the urgent need for a national conversation about what it means to be a Professor and subsequently, a move for the streamlining of standards and titles in South Africa’s knowledge industry.

In South Africa, there are associate and senior professors at some universities whose publication record is almost zero. I know some senior professors who have published only four or five journal articles. Some of them have not presented papers at the conferences for six or ten years. For some of these professors to apply to NRF for rating, their rating will be very low. It is my view that they may be regarded as promising scholars. Some university professors – whether associate or senior – are not scholars and their academic standing is not even befitting the title of a professor. Unfortunately, the system, which is not solid in terms of quality, has ways or means of reproducing itself. Assuming that South Africa’s knowledge industry has some professors who are not scholars but are in leadership positions, they are likely to undermine scholarship by promoting mediocrity. The foregoing analysis should be understood within the context of the new trend in South Africa wherein some individuals without PhDs are even awarded Professorships [22].

Fortunately, the editorial leadership of the journal referred to above enjoy unquestionable national recognition in Public Affairs circles. While google metric is not the only criteria to determine one’s academic merit, it is shocking, that scholars with over sixty publications in different peer reviewed platforms are still referred to as “promising”, which technically suggests that they are still emerging. Besides this, the editor in chief is currently a faculty executive dean and the deputy is a school director. Surely, their elevation to this position also attests to their impeccable scholarly credentials and to refer to them as not established raises a lot of questions than answers.

Just like the composition of some of the NRF rating panels is questionable, the make-up of the ASSAf review panel of some of the journals in South Africa is worrisome [20]. It is this very fact that makes their adverse findings of some journals predicted and/or concocted to achieve a narrow and short-term goal. According to such Kangaroo journal review panels, the editorial board of some journals (especially those, led by editors with different views, from those, held by ASSAf leadership) is largely deficient of members with international standing. Such outlandish claims are normally without regard of the fact that there is established or prescribed minimum number of non-South African scholars that ought to be in a journal’s editorial board for it to qualify as reputable. This shows the narrow and/or biased conception of the such panels in terms of international recognition. It is in the nature of some of the NRF rating panels and ASSAf journal panels to condemn publications by students or citations by students. As academics, we do not dictate who should cite our work. If students and/or colleagues find it suitable for their studies, one cannot stop them as s/he may not be aware of their on-going research projects.

It is possible, that ASSAf consists of individuals who are not solid scholars. If it is true that they are not solid scholars, they will empower their colleagues and friends who are also not solid scholars as a way to protect themselves and for the organisation to be used in protecting themselves. The organisation seems to be dominated not by Social Scientists, but by applied scientists. The marginalisation of Social Sciences, particularly Political Science and Public Affairs Scholars, is such that ASSAf is an organisation, used in marginalising Social Scientists, particularly Political Scientists and Public Affairs Scholars.

Equally important, journal articles are assessed and published based on their quality as reflected in blind peer review reports. The status and/or position of the author in society is really not an issue in this regard. While a certain journal may publish the work of senior academics, it cannot be embarrassed by the fact that it welcomes quality contributions by emerging scholars who tend to work hand in glove with their mentors. In fact, some students write better journal articles than some professors. As such, journals embracing the contributions of emerging scholars are unnecessarily lamented. Typical of Western scholarship, there is an expectation on the part of some of ASSAf (and NRF) panels for researchers/ journals to follow the so-called empiricist path as means of elevating their status at the international level [20]. This type of observation is worrisome, it does not appreciate the evolution of knowledge from positivism, post-modernism to decoloniality.

Of contextual interest is that journals that are edited by those with proximity to corridors of power in NRF and ASSAf are always commended. If this is anything to go by, then Steve Biko's words that "Black man you are on your own" [15] are louder now than ever. Perhaps, the foregoing analysis provides a partial guide to the understanding of the account of very few Black South African rated scholars in Public Affairs. Those who preside over decisions in this regard have proven to be either emanating from non-Public Affairs disciplines. This brings us to the illogicality (as propagated by ASSAf and NRF) of clubbing Public Affairs with Management Sciences, which hardly appreciate the nature and form of research in the former, especially those studies that are anchored on theoretical, textual and historical analysis [1]. This challenge is not limited to ASSAf. It can also be observed in some universities' executive committees wherein unfair decisions without regard of "articulation without discipline" are made.

3. 3. Universities – research council's interface

Universities and research councils occupy a strategic position in terms of knowledge generation and development in South Africa [1]. Inasmuch as they are autonomous, they enjoy a sustainable flow of state funds in support of the development and growth of the knowledge industry in South Africa. In this section of the paper, I wish to limit myself to selected challenges that weaken the academic project and yet, have not received adequate scholarly attention. A case in point is the demoralisation of academics due to arbitrary delays and/or denial for promotion [23]. I am reminded of the promotion of certain cohort of academics at a particular university, which was held in abeyance in order to cut down the cost of salary increments that follow the promotion. Related to such shenanigans, a certain academic's promotion application was questioned on funny grounds. This academic was employed at this university as an Associate Professor in Political Science. But when the time for his/her application for Full Professorship had to be considered, those entrusted with authority to make decisions in this regard raised the issue that the applicant's Doctoral qualification was in International Politics. Those who are in this space will tell you that this debate is equivalent to that of chicken and egg. Hence, International Politics is a branch of the mother discipline of Political Science. These dynamics demoralise academics and take away their motivation to strive for enhanced scholarly performance and excellence [24].

Some individuals who are not Political Scientists or Public Affairs scholars are influential in South Africa, especially at our universities. As a result, they make critical decisions affecting Political Science and Public Affairs when they do not have any glue about these disciplines. Related to this, at another university some executive committee's position is that there is no articulation between Strategic Management and International Politics. In the same breath, issues relating to Africa are victims in this process. Some individuals claim to be experts on them. They are also regarded as experts on them by their cheer followers while they are not. The foregoing analysis is reflective of the extent of the damage, caused to the pursuit of true knowledge by the de-professionalisation of academic disciplines, such as Political Science and Public Affairs.

In another university in South Africa, the buck in terms of promotion stops with the Vice Chancellor and Principal. Senate and other institutional committees only exist as a formality. The Vice Chancellor and Principal commands so much power and authority that s/he will willy-nilly rejects applications for academic promotion without any sound basis. But no one within the Management Committee (ManCo) will dare challenge him/her. In this institution, the culture of fear is prevalent. Those who previously disagreed with Vice Chancellor and Principal were persecuted through suspensions or non-renewal of contracts. It is such a precedence that has softly killed scholarly freedom at this university. Despite glaring evidence of the abuse of power on the part of the Vice Chancellor and Principal, s/he never faces any consequences as most of the council members are beholden to her/him as they indirectly benefit from his/her evil patronage system. To add, some of the council members are neither serious scholars nor administrators. Therefore, they cannot help the universities by effectively and efficiently executing their fiduciary duties. The labour union is also weakened and/or compromised by the fear of victimisation or through entanglement to the evil patronage system of the Vice Chancellor and Principal. This practice is not limited to one uni-

iversity in South Africa. It just assumes different forms in different campuses. It is also not a new development in South Africa as it also happened during the apartheid era [1].

In the same breath, researchers, attached to research councils, are also faced with the mountain of a challenge of being demoralised as a result of unprecedented institutional changes. A case in point is the incorporation of then Africa Institute of South Africa (AISA) into the HSRC. This rationalisation was argued by the government as driven by the imperatives to save and maximise available resources. No matter the genuine intentions of this move, it has produced resistance and demoralisation among the staff, attached to AISA. Following the incorporation, AISA was relegated to the status of a unit within HSRC. The broader mandate of HSRC has meant that AISA is technically swallowed up in terms of mandate and/or focus on Africa to a point wherein it has in fact lost its distinctive identity, which was established over many decades.

Limitations of the study and prospects for further research. The conduction of this study was hampered by minor constraints. For example, this study was not funded. Therefore, it relied on the slender resource base of the researcher. This did not affect the admissibility and reliability of the findings of this paper's research. This paper paints a qualitatively rich but skeletal picture of South Africa's contemporary knowledge production regime. As such, it serves a stepping stone for future research on this subject. This subject could be revisited with a different theoretical lens and/or with a comparative approach. Alternatively, large scale interviews with key informants within South Africa's knowledge industry could also be considered.

4. Conclusion

One of the key reasons why statutory institutions do not respect public or national policies is because a considerable number of members of parliament are not policymakers. They cannot be regarded as policymakers. While reading and writing capacity of some is at a lower level, that of others is zero. Most of South Africa's senior state officials, such as director generals, do not publish even newspaper articles. Basically, they do not read serious literature, such as journal articles. The consequence is that it is difficult if not impossible to hold statutory institutions accountable. While this challenges are endemic in South Africa, they could be observed in other parts of the world.

AISA is the victim of the South African state. It is interesting, that a country whose governing party (African National Congress) from time to time make declarations about Africa has incorporated AISA, an internationally rated organisation and well-known organisation throughout Africa into HSRC, an organisation which is not internationally rated and not well-known throughout Africa. The South African state did not understand the consequence of its decision of incorporating AISA into HSRC.

In the case of the universities, one wonders how can they best and most effectively do justice in advancing South Africa's popular interests as an African country, while it has failed to solve problems, faced by African academics working at them. DHET has been appointing task team after task team on problems, faced by African academics of South Africa at the South African universities. The department itself has hopelessly failed in solving these problems. What is interesting is that these universities are largely funded by the South African state. The South African state has failed to use its funding of the universities to ensure that they do what is right particularly to African academics of South Africa. With capable representatives, parliament's portfolio committee on Higher Education, Training, Science and Innovation may exercise the legislative power to ensure that the universities and other statutory institutions do what is right and respect laws of this country.

In conclusion, this desktop paper has sought to explore the dynamics of selected statutory institutions and their implications for knowledge development in South Africa. It has adopted an interdisciplinary discourse analysis, insider's perspective and Afrocentricity as a contextual lens, geared towards the painting of an alternative and qualitatively rich picture of the phenomena studied. Emerging from the above, it has been established, that the triage of ASSAf, NRF and universities – research councils has been birthed with good intentions including but not limited to the promotion of scholarship in South Africa. Despite this, inter-group dynamics with grounds on race, ideology, politics and managerialism have tempered with the very essence of the academic project – the pursuit or service of truth. Some of the issues, raised in this regard, are well known within the

academic circles but are downplayed or less talked about due to the fear of possible reprisals from the corridors of power in ASSAf, NRF and universities – research councils. In order to evade the trappings of this academic quagmire, targeted transformation initiatives and interventions within these institutions should be considered as a matter of urgency. The list of statutory institutions studied herein is not exhaustive. Therefore, this paper cannot be a last word on this subject. This subject can be revisited with a focus on other statutory institutions and can be extended through field research.

In the final analysis, a question can be posed: What is South Africa doing well or poorly in the knowledge sector in comparison to its peers elsewhere? Based on the findings of the research of this paper, it is submitted the important issue that it is not necessary what South Africa does well or not compared to others, but the choices, imposed upon her by the matrix of coloniality. Unlike South Africa's peers in the Global North or South, South Africa spent efforts doing the unnecessary. Instead of being leaders in the society by providing direction, its universities and other key institutions in the knowledge industry do not live up to their essence because they have not been genuinely established to do so. Hence, universities in South Africa are by and large, extensions of the system of imperialism. For this reasons, these institutions are not true to their civilisation, culture and history; an unfortunate situation that produced a relapse of the country's knowledge industry, which almost warrants an endless rendition for decolonisation and Africanisation.

Conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Funding

The study was conceptualised and operationalised without any financial support.

Data availability

Manuscript has no associated data.

References

- [1] Higgins, J. (2013). *Academic Freedom in a Democratic South Africa*. Johannesburg: Wits University Press, 272.
- [2] About ASSAf. ASSAf. Available at: <https://www.assaf.org.za/index.php/about-assaf/about-assaf> Last accessed: 12.03.2021
- [3] HSRC Act. HSRC. Available at: <http://www.hsrc.ac.za/en/about/hsrc-act> Last accessed: 13.03.2021
- [4] Mandate. NRF. Available at: <https://www.nrf.ac.za/about-us/>
- [5] Annual Reports. HSRC. Available at: <https://hsrc.ac.za/who-we-are/strategic-documents/>
- [6] Motau, K. (2018). SAAPAM Chief Editor 'threatened' after rejection of some articles. *Eyewitness News*. Available at: <https://ewn.co.za/2018/03/03/saapam-chief-editor-threatened-after-rejection-of-some-articles> Last accessed: 03.03.2018
- [7] Sithole, M. P. (2009). *Unequal Peers*. Pretoria: Africa Institute of South Africa.
- [8] Asante, M. K. (2003). *Afrocentricity: The Theory of Social Change*. Chicago: African American Images.
- [9] Mazama, A. (Ed.) (2003). *The Afrocentric Paradigm*. Trenton: Africa World Press.
- [10] Azibo, D. A. (2011). Understanding Essentialism as Fundamental: The Centred African Perspective on the Nature of Prototypical Human Nature- Cosmological Ka (Spirit). *The Western Journal of Black Studies*, 35 (2), 77–91.
- [11] Shai, K. B. (2020). Heteroglossia of Changing Scholarship in South Africa: In defence of the Afrocentric Archive. *African Journal of Gender, Society and Development*, 9 (3), 175–188. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31920/2634-3622/2020/9n3a8>
- [12] Maserumule, M. H. (2011). *Good Governance in the New Partnership for Africa's Development NEPAD: A Public Administration Perspective*. Pretoria: University of South Africa.
- [13] Legodi, L. T., Shai, K. B. (2021). (Re)Visiting Molefi Kete Asante's Theory of Afrocentricity. In Zondi, S. *African Voices in Search of a Decolonial Turn*. Pretoria: Human Sciences Research Council, 152–168.
- [14] *Members of Rating Panels and Meeting Dates (2020)*. NRF.
- [15] Badat, S. (2009). *Black Man, you are on your own*. Braamfontein: Steve Biko Foundation.
- [16] Article in *City Press* by Msindisi Fengu *How dodgy academics rake in the buck* (2018). ASSAf & Universities South Africa. City Press.

- [17] Mudau, J., Mokgokong, M. J., Khanya, M. P. (2021). Gerentocracy and the Fourth Industrial Revolution in the Public Sector Amid the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Perennial Problem. *European Journal of Economics, Law and Social Sciences*, 27–43.
- [18] Minutes of an Extraordinary General Meeting of Members of South African Association of Public Administration and Management (SAAPAM) (2010). South African Association of Public Administration and Management (SAAPAM). Villa Sterne.
- [19] Vale, P. (2014). Presentation. Critical Perspectives on the ASSAf Humanities Consensus Report, Human and Social Dynamics (HSD) Research Seminar Series, Co-hosted by the Department of Science and Technology & HSRC. CSIR Conference Centre.
- [20] Consensus Report on Grouped Peer Review of Scholarly Journals in Economics and Business Management (2021). *Journal of Public Administration Draft Report*. ASSAf.
- [21] Makgatho, L. (2022). Workplace debate leads to lawsuit and claim for damages. Available at: <https://www.iol.co.za/sunday-independent/news/workplace-debate-leads-to-lawsuit-and-claim-for-damages-3bb6fb00-191d-4287-a047-bbb18e1f5b1d> Last accessed: 15.08.2022
- [22] Résumé: Bonang F. Mohale (2022). University of Pretoria. <https://www.up.ac.za/media/shared/Legacy/sitefiles/file/rsum-bonangmohale.pdf> Last accessed: 15.08.2022
- [23] B. Shai, K. (2020). Mokoko Sebola on ‘Scientific Knowledge in Africa’ : an Afrocentric Critique. *African Renaissance*, 17 (1), 143–156. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31920/2516-5305/2020/17n1a7>
- [24] Shai, K. B. (2021). *Scholarship and Politics in South Africa’s Higher Education System*. London: Adonis & Abbey Publishers, 162.

Received date 15.12.2022

Accepted date 19.01.2023

Published date 30.01.2023

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How to cite: Shai, K. B. (2023). *An afrocentric critique of South Africa’s contemporary knowledge production regime*. *EUREKA: Social and Humanities*, 1, 72–80. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5571.2023.002542>